

The Use of Psychedelic Drugs in the Treatment of Unipolar Depression

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Introduction

Depression is a common group of psychiatric disorders with a highly diverse clinical presentation and, in many cases, a severe course. It is estimated that approximately 280 million people worldwide suffer from depression. The course of depression can vary significantly, with the most frequently reported symptoms including low mood, anhedonia, and feelings of reduced energy.

Objective

The aim of this study is to assess the effectiveness of currently used antidepressant treatment methods and compare them to the antidepressant effects of ketamine, MDMA, and psilocybin.

Review

methods

A review of scientific literature available on the PubMed platform was conducted using the following keywords: depression, psychedelic drugs, treatment of depression, treatment-resistant depression. Twenty-one articles published in the last 5 years were searched and analyzed.

Abbreviated description and the state of knowledge

In the treatment of depression, the most commonly used methods include pharmacotherapy with various classes of antidepressant medications and psychotherapy. The efficacy of pharmacotherapy with a single drug is estimated at 60%, with only 30% of patients remaining completely symptom-free within 12 weeks of therapy. To increase efficacy, pharmacotherapy involving at least two classes of antidepressants is used. A major limitation of classical pharmacotherapy is the frequent occurrence of adverse effects during treatment. Psychotherapy, used as one of the first-line therapeutic methods, shows effectiveness comparable to pharmacotherapy. The relatively high ineffectiveness of classical pharmacotherapy and psychotherapy necessitates the search for new therapeutic methods.

Conclusions

Psychedelic drugs demonstrate significant efficacy in the treatment of unipolar depressive disorders and have a high safety profile. A particular advantage of psychedelic drugs is their rapid action compared to classical pharmacotherapy.

Key words: depression, treatment-resistant depression, psychedelic drugs, pharmacotherapy,

Depression is a commonly occurring group of psychiatric disorders that develop within a complex framework involving psychological, neurological, immunological, and endocrinological factors.[1] It is estimated that approximately 280 million people worldwide are affected by depression.[2] Classifications of depressive disorders vary and lead to significant controversies among proponents of different classification systems for this group of diseases. Among the most frequently used classification systems globally, the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems 10th revision (ICD-10) and Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5) are particularly prevalent. The system most commonly used in Poland is the ICD-10 classification proposed by the World Health Organization (WHO), which includes the following categories for unipolar depressive disorders:

- **F32** - Depressive Episode (mild, moderate, severe without psychotic symptoms, severe with psychotic symptoms, other depressive episodes, unspecified depressive episode)
- **F33** - Recurrent Depressive Disorder (currently a mild episode, currently a moderate episode, currently a severe depressive episode without psychotic symptoms, currently a severe depressive episode with psychotic symptoms, currently in remission, other recurrent depressive disorders, unspecified recurrent depressive disorder) [3]

The most common symptoms observed in patients with unipolar depressive disorders include: low mood, loss of interest and anhedonia, reduced energy. Additionally, there may be impaired concentration, low self-esteem, feelings of guilt, suicidal thoughts and behaviors, sleep disturbances, and reduced appetite.[1] Among the primary treatment methods for depressive disorders, pharmacotherapy and psychotherapy are distinguished.

The aim of this study is to assess the effectiveness of currently used antidepressant treatments and compare them to the antidepressant effects of ketamine, MDMA, and psilocybin.

The analysis includes studies available in the PubMed database published over the last 5 years.

Among the most commonly used drugs in the treatment of depressive disorders, the following are distinguished:

Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors(SSRIs), serotonin-norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors(SNRIs), tricyclic antidepressants(TCAs), norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors(NRIs), and norepinephrine-dopamine reuptake inhibitors(NDRIs)[1],[4].

Classical pharmacotherapy, typically involving a single drug, results in improvement in 60% of patients, of which only 30% are symptom-free within the first 12 weeks of therapy. To enhance effectiveness, combination pharmacotherapy using more than one class of antidepressants is employed. However, even one-third of patients do not respond to this approach and continue to present with disease symptoms[5],[6],[7],[8]. A significant limitation of classical pharmacotherapy is the frequent occurrence of adverse effects. Among the most commonly used class of antidepressants (SSRIs), which have the safest side-effect profile, gastrointestinal symptoms are common, including: dyspepsia (22%), nausea (18%), diarrhea (9%), constipation (11%) [7].

Psychotherapy, alongside pharmacotherapy, is a first-line treatment in all age groups. It encompasses a variety of support forms, which often differ significantly from each other. Among the main psychotherapy approaches are: cognitive-behavioral, psychodynamic, interpersonal, and others. The estimated effectiveness of psychotherapy methods is comparable to that of pharmacotherapy, and furthermore, the strategy combining psychotherapy and pharmacotherapy has proven to be more effective than monotherapy based on either psycho- or pharmacotherapy alone.

One non-pharmacological method of treating depression currently undergoing intensive research is deep brain stimulation (DBS), which has already demonstrated proven efficacy and is a standard treatment in other disorders, such as idiopathic Parkinson's disease[9].

The relatively high ineffectiveness of pharmacotherapy, combined with its numerous adverse effects, has led to the search for new classes of drugs that offer a better safety profile and greater efficacy.[10] In recent years, there has been a resurgence of interest in psychedelic substances, which are purported to exhibit antidepressant effects with relatively mild adverse effects. Psilocybin, LSD, 3,4-methylenedioxymethamphetamine (MDMA), and ketamine are representatives of the psychedelic drug class that have undergone the most extensive clinical research to investigate the presence and potential strength of their antidepressant effects.[11],[12]

Ketamine

Ketamine is a non-competitive NMDA receptor antagonist commonly used in anesthesiology and emergency medicine as a drug with both hypnotic and analgesic properties. It may be present in its racemic form (ketamine) or as esketamine.

There are two main hypotheses explaining the antidepressant effects of ketamine. The first posits that ketamine increases presynaptic glutamate release in the medial prefrontal cortex by blocking presynaptic NMDA receptors on inhibitory neurons. The second theory suggests that ketamine enhances the synaptic efficacy of the hippocampus by blocking NMDA receptors on the postsynaptic membrane of excitatory neurons in the hippocampal Schaffer-collateral pathway [5].

When administered at subanesthetic doses, ketamine produces antidepressant effects within hours of administration, which can last for over a week (with some effects extending up to 4 weeks) [5,13,14]. It is estimated that the efficacy of ketamine and esketamine is similar, resulting in improvements in depression severity ($d = -0.63$; 95% CI, -0.80 to -0.45 ; $I^2 = 78\%$), disease remission (RR = 1.64; 95% CI, 1.33–2.02; $I^2 = 39\%$), and treatment efficacy in the final phase (RR = 2.14; 95% CI, 1.72–2.66; $I^2 = 65\%$) [15]. A single dose of ketamine leads to clinical improvement in 50-70% of patients on the first day [12]. One of the most significant characteristics of ketamine is its rapid antidepressant action, which is highly important because classical pharmacotherapy often requires many weeks of administration to achieve an

effect. Additionally, meta-analyses have demonstrated that ketamine use reduces the risk of suicide for up to 4 weeks post-administration, with this finding being statistically significant [12],[13],[14].

Psilocybin

Psilocybin is a naturally occurring alkaloid with a structure based on tryptamine, containing an indole ring. It is commonly found worldwide in over 200 species of mushrooms, primarily of the *Psilocybe* genus, which are commonly referred to as magic mushrooms. Its metabolism occurs in the liver, where active metabolites are released, and their elimination primarily takes place through renal excretion. Psilocybin is a prodrug, which, upon dephosphorylation, gains a high affinity for the serotonin 2A receptor, with a weaker affinity for other serotonin receptors [16]. After crossing the blood-brain barrier and binding to receptors, it increases intracellular signaling activity in cortical pyramidal neurons, modifying various intracellular pathways. Studies on the effectiveness of psilocybin in treating unipolar depressive disorders have employed a wide range of doses, from 1 mg/70 kg, which serves as a placebo, to 50 mg/70 kg [2],[17]. Research indicates that psilocybin significantly reduces the severity of depressive symptoms after one or two doses. Improvement was felt almost immediately after the first dose and one week after the second dose. Clinical improvement lasted up to a year after administration.

High doses of psilocybin, compared to placebo and low doses, demonstrated higher efficacy (significant improvement on the Beck Depression Inventory in the group receiving higher doses compared to their baseline pre-therapy scores: $M = 34.44(7.44)$ vs. $12.13(9.8)$; $g = 1.9$, $p < 0.001$). This effect was equalized when the lower doses were increased to higher ones [2]. Primary depressive disorders, in contrast to secondary ones caused by other conditions, exhibited higher resistance to lower doses of psilocybin (ED95% for the primary depression group was achieved at a dose of 24.68 mg/70 kg, while for the secondary depression group, ED95% was much lower, achieved at a dose of 8.92 mg/70 kg) [17].

Similar results were obtained when niacin was used as a placebo instead of psilocybin at a dose of 1 mg/70 kg [18]. Analysis of therapy efficacy after 6 weeks showed no statistically significant differences between the groups treated with the classical first-line SSRI (escitalopram) and psilocybin [19], and no major side effects were observed, with mild adverse effects such as nausea and headaches [20],[21].

MDMA

MDMA (3,4-methylenedioxymethamphetamine) is a synthetic derivative of amphetamine, commonly known as Ecstasy, exhibiting a range of central nervous system (CNS) effects, including acting as a serotonin receptor agonist, a substance that enhances serotonin and norepinephrine release, and a reuptake inhibitor for serotonin, norepinephrine, and dopamine.

In recent years, numerous studies have demonstrated the efficacy of MDMA therapy in the treatment of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), owing to its effects, which include euphoria and pro-social behaviors [12],[16],[22],[23]. During these studies, an additional impact of MDMA on depressive disorders was discovered, as they are present in up to 42.9% of patients diagnosed with PTSD [22].

An additional clinical trial focused on this effect showed the efficacy of MDMA in reducing the severity of unipolar depressive disorders, as assessed by the Montgomery-Åsberg Depression Rating Scale (-14.6 versus -20.9, and -0.7 and -10.5 for the placebo and MDMA groups, respectively). The therapy was well tolerated, with no serious adverse effects observed, and mild adverse effects including decreased appetite, muscle stiffness, nausea, and hypertrichosis [22,23].

Conclusions

Despite the broad range of treatment methods for unipolar depressive disorders, including pharmacotherapy with antidepressant medications, psychotherapy, and deep brain stimulation, many therapeutic challenges remain. These include, among others, a relatively high rate of treatment resistance, significant adverse effects of the medications used, and delayed therapeutic effects. The use of psychedelic substances could potentially eliminate or at least reduce some of these challenges; however, they still require further research, particularly focusing on potential adverse effects. An additional issue is the unclear legal status of these substances, which significantly varies depending on the country and the policies surrounding the prevention of their use for recreational purposes or from unknown sources.

Bibliography

- [1] Dobrek L, Głowacka K. Depression and Its Phytopharmacotherapy-A Narrative Review. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2023 Mar 1;24(5):4772. doi: 10.3390/ijms24054772. PMID: 36902200; PMCID: PMC10003400.
- [2] Dawood Hristova JJ, Pérez-Jover V. Psychotherapy with Psilocybin for Depression: Systematic Review. *Behav Sci (Basel).* 2023 Mar 31;13(4):297. doi: 10.3390/bs13040297. PMID: 37102811; PMCID: PMC10135952.
- [3] ICD-10 Version:2016. (n.d.). *Icd.who.int.* <https://icd.who.int/browse10/2016/en#/F64> (access 2025.01.16).
- [4] Steffens DC. Treatment-Resistant Depression in Older Adults. *N Engl J Med.* 2024 Feb 15;390(7):630-639. doi: 10.1056/NEJMcp2305428. PMID: 38354142; PMCID: PMC10885705.
- [5] Kim JW, Suzuki K, Kavalali ET, Monteggia LM. Ketamine: Mechanisms and Relevance to Treatment of Depression. *Annu Rev Med.* 2024 Jan 29;75:129-143. doi: 10.1146/annurev-med-051322-120608. Epub 2023 Sep 20. PMID: 37729028.
- [6] Papp M, Cubala WJ, Swiecicki L, Newman-Tancredi A, Willner P. Perspectives for therapy of treatment-resistant depression. *Br J Pharmacol.* 2022 Sep;179(17):4181-4200. doi: 10.1111/bph.15596. Epub 2021 Jul 29. PMID: 34128229.
- [7] Ramic E, Prasko S, Gavran L, Spahic E. Assessment of the Antidepressant Side Effects Occurrence in Patients Treated in Primary Care. *Mater Sociomed.* 2020 Jun;32(2):131-134. doi: 10.5455/msm.2020.32.131-134. PMID: 32843862; PMCID: PMC7428926.
- [8] Touloumis C. The burden and the challenge of treatment-resistant depression. *Psychiatriki.* 2021 Dec;32(Supplement 1):11-14. English, Greek, Modern. doi: 10.22365/jpsych.2021.046. PMID: 34990376.
- [9] Figeo M, Riva-Posse P, Choi KS, Bederson L, Mayberg HS, Kopell BH. Deep Brain Stimulation for Depression. *Neurotherapeutics.* 2022 Jul;19(4):1229-1245. doi: 10.1007/s13311-022-01270-3. Epub 2022 Jul 11. PMID: 35817944; PMCID: PMC9587188.
- [10] Cuijpers P, Miguel C, Harrer M, Plessen CY, Ciharova M, Papola D, Ebert D, Karyotaki E. Psychological treatment of depression: A systematic overview of a 'Meta-Analytic Research Domain'. *J Affect Disord.* 2023 Aug 15;335:141-151. doi: 10.1016/j.jad.2023.05.011. Epub 2023 May 11. PMID: 37178828.
- [11] Nutt D. Psychedelic drugs-a new era in psychiatry? . *Dialogues Clin Neurosci.* 2019;21(2):139-147. doi: 10.31887/DCNS.2019.21.2/dnutt. PMID: 31636488; PMCID: PMC6787540.
- [12] De Gregorio D, Aguilar-Valles A, Preller KH, Heifets BD, Hibicke M, Mitchell J, Gobbi G. Hallucinogens in Mental Health: Preclinical and Clinical Studies on LSD, Psilocybin, MDMA, and Ketamine. *J Neurosci.* 2021 Feb 3;41(5):891-900. doi: 10.1523/JNEUROSCI.1659-20.2020. Epub 2020 Nov 30. PMID: 33257322; PMCID: PMC7880300.
- [13] Psiuk D, Nowak EM, Dycha N, Łopuszańska U, Kurzepa J, Samardakiewicz M. Esketamine and Psilocybin-The Comparison of Two Mind-Altering Agents in Depression Treatment: Systematic Review. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2022 Sep 28;23(19):11450. doi: 10.3390/ijms231911450. PMID: 36232748; PMCID: PMC9570062.
- [14] Bahji A, Vazquez GH, Zarate CA Jr. Comparative efficacy of racemic ketamine and esketamine for depression: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Affect Disord.* 2021 Jan 1;278:542-555. doi: 10.1016/j.jad.2020.09.071. Epub 2020 Sep 23. Erratum in: *J Affect Disord.* 2021 Feb 15;281:1001. doi: 10.1016/j.jad.2020.11.103. PMID: 33022440; PMCID: PMC7704936.
- [15] Bahji A, Zarate CA, Vazquez GH. Efficacy and safety of racemic ketamine and esketamine for depression: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Expert Opin Drug Saf.* 2022 Jun;21(6):853-866. doi: 10.1080/14740338.2022.2047928. Epub 2022 Mar 9. PMID: 35231204; PMCID: PMC9949988.
- [16] Bosch OG, Halm S, Seifritz E. Psychedelics in the treatment of unipolar and bipolar depression. *Int J Bipolar Disord.* 2022 Jul 5;10(1):18. doi: 10.1186/s40345-022-00265-5. PMID: 35788817; PMCID: PMC9256889.
- [17] Perez N, Langlest F, Mallet L, De Pieri M, Sentissi O, Thorens G, Seragnoli F, Zullino D, Kirschner M, Kaiser S, Solmi M, Sabé M. Psilocybin-assisted therapy for depression: A systematic review and dose-response meta-analysis of

human studies. *Eur Neuropsychopharmacol.* 2023 Nov;76:61-76. doi: 10.1016/j.euroneuro.2023.07.011. Epub 2023 Aug 7. PMID: 37557019.

[18] Ross S, Bossis A, Guss J, Agin-Liebes G, Malone T, Cohen B, Mennenga SE, Belser A, Kalliontzi K, Babb J, Su Z, Corby P, Schmidt BL. Rapid and sustained symptom reduction following psilocybin treatment for anxiety and depression in patients with life-threatening cancer: a randomized controlled trial. *J Psychopharmacol.* 2016 Dec;30(12):1165-1180. doi: 10.1177/0269881116675512. PMID: 27909164; PMCID: PMC5367551.

[19] Bancroft HR, Moore CA, Frazier JL. Development of a biochemical profile for mass-reared boll weevils (Coleoptera: Curculionidae). *Comp Biochem Physiol C Comp Pharmacol.* 1976;53(1):9-12. doi: 10.1016/0306-4492(76)90041-1. PMID: 3385.

[20] Johannesdottir A, Sigurdsson E. [The use of psilocybin for treatment-resistant depression]. *Laeknabladid.* 2022 Sep;108(9):403-410. Icelandic. doi: 10.17992/ibl.2022.09.706. PMID: 36040772.

[21] Irizarry R, Winczura A, Dimassi O, Dhillon N, Minhas A, Larice J. Psilocybin as a Treatment for Psychiatric Illness: A Meta-Analysis. *Cureus.* 2022 Nov 22;14(11):e31796. doi: 10.7759/cureus.31796. PMID: 36569662; PMCID: PMC9779908.

[22] Psiuk D, Nowak E, Cholewa K, Łopuszańska U, Samardakiewicz M. The Potential Role of Serotonergic Hallucinogens in Depression Treatment. *Life (Basel).* 2021 Jul 29;11(8):765. doi: 10.3390/life11080765. PMID: 34440508; PMCID: PMC8400004.

[23] Mitchell JM, Bogenschutz M, Lilienstein A, Harrison C, Kleiman S, Parker-Guilbert K, Ot'alora G M, Garas W, Paleos C, Gorman I, Nicholas C, Mithoefer M, Carlin S, Poulter B, Mithoefer A, Quevedo S, Wells G, Klaire SS, van der Kolk B, Tzarfaty K, Amiaz R, Worthy R, Shannon S, Woolley JD, Marta C, Gelfand Y, Hapke E, Amar S, Wallach Y, Brown R, Hamilton S, Wang JB, Coker A, Matthews R, de Boer A, Yazar-Klosinski B, Emerson A, Doblin R. MDMA-assisted therapy for severe PTSD: a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled phase 3 study. *Nat Med.* 2021 Jun;27(6):1025-1033. doi: 10.1038/s41591-021-01336-3. Epub 2021 May 10. PMID: 33972795; PMCID: PMC8205851.